

Social innovation for sustainable rural communities: overcoming institutional challenges in Serbia

Ivana Zivojinovic¹, Karl Hogl², Gerhard Weiss¹, Alice Ludvig¹

¹Institute of Forest, Environment and Natural Resource Policy, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU) and European Forest Institute, Forest Policy Research Network, Vienna, Austria; ²Institute of Forest, Environment and Natural (ivana.zivojinovic@boku.ac.at; karl.hogl@boku.ac.at; gerhard.weiss@boku.ac.at; alice.ludvig@boku.ac.at)

Today's world society is facing a number of longstanding challenges, such as poverty, famine, inequalities, environmental challenges, and migration, which call for new and creative responses that stimulate change and are often lacking in traditional governmental approaches. Social innovations are such responses that can offer social-ecological and economic solutions to mitigate social problems by introducing new practices. They are highly relevant for rural communities for reducing social inequalities and disproportionate resource use, and fostering sustainable development. Understanding the role of social innovation is especially complicated in unstable institutional environments, e.g. in developing, post-war, or countries in transition. This paper, firstly, traces institutional voids related to social innovation in Serbia, such as a relatively poor legitimacy and enforcement of the rule of law, and institutions that fail to address societal needs. Secondly, it analyses ten cases of social innovations in rural areas, related also to forestry sector, based on in-depth interviews and document analysis. The analysis contributes to the understanding of factors that facilitate and constrain social innovations, but also efforts of social innovators to overcome institutional voids. Our results show that some types of social innovation are more likely to fill in institutional gaps and to create social values while others are oriented to secure economic benefits. Furthermore, the need for context-specific structures that enable and foster social innovations is emphasised, including improved legal frameworks (e.g. forestry and rural development related policies), favourable tax regulations and innovative financial mechanisms, which allow implementing social innovations in rural communities.